

Mentoring II

Q1 We are a team of computer science researchers investigating the benefits of informal mentoring in open-source communities. Your input will help us identify how mentoring occurs implicitly in day-to-day tasks in open-source communities and its benefits.

This survey should take approximately 5-10 minutes to complete. The results of this survey will be used in a scientific publication. There will also be a question at the end of the survey for you to indicate if you would like to receive a copy of any publications or reports generated from this study. By clicking the button below, you acknowledge that your participation in the study is voluntary, you are at least 18 years of age, and that you are aware that you may choose to terminate your participation in the study at any time and for any reason. If you have any questions or concerns, please contact...

EEA Data Privacy: Participants in the EEA are advised that data privacy laws have not been deemed adequate by the European Commission. For more information, participants can contact...

I consent

I do not consent

Implicit mentoring can occur in everyday development activities like code reviews, where a mentor ***implicitly*** provides mentoring by giving an explanation when providing suggestions, instructions, or mechanisms to address errors. In contrast, explicit mentoring is where mentees seek out a mentor or are formally paired with mentors.

Given the definition above, please indicate whether the following PR comments include (implicit) mentoring:

Q2 **PR Comment 1:** "Did you take note of the discussion on the dev mailing list? Would you mind going the extra step to update other tests that might be a problem (you're likely to run into them later as you continue with your implementation anyway)?"

--- GitHub Pull-request comment (user: spmallette)

Mentoring, why? _____

Not mentoring, why? _____

Not sure

Q3 **PR Comment 2:** "I think changes like this need to be discussed beforehand on the dev mailing list or on the JIRA issue. This would configure a build on a Windows machine using GitHub actions. I don't think we need this, at least not in this form."

--- GitHub Pull-request comment (user: zregvart)

Mentoring, why? _____

Not mentoring, why? _____

Not sure

Q4 PR Comment 3: "I think this is better than reverting the three commits."

--- GitHub Pull-request comment (user: aljoscha)

Mentoring, why? _____

Not mentoring, why? _____

Not sure

Q5 PR Comment 4: "Thanks for this PR, but: Is this needed? Do 7 chars less per line change something? - It impacts a lot of files for IMO rather very low value and could make regression analysis more complex knowing we have already changed a huge amount of code."

--- GitHub Pull-request comment (user: pmouawad)

Mentoring, why? _____

Not mentoring, why? _____

Not sure

Q6 PR Comment 5: "Yeah, I don't know what things Kafka improve from Spark script so I wanted to see the benefit if you know about it. As I commented earlier, just adopting script doesn't work since we use different branch models (master, minor, bugfix) so it should be fully tested (including JIRA integration) before adopting."

--- GitHub Pull-request comment (user: HeartSaVioR)

Mentoring, why? _____

Not mentoring, why? _____

Not sure

Q7 PR Comment 6: "@swill @milamberspace weird, we've lost our Travis integration with PRs here. <https://travis-ci.org/apache/cloudstack/> says "The repository at apache/cloudstack was not found"

--- GitHub Pull-request comment (user: rhtyd)

Mentoring, why? _____

Not mentoring, why? _____

Not sure

Q8 PR Comment 7: "ClassInfo#remove is fine, adding it to InvokerHelper#removeClass is probably fine too. Doing this to Eval is probably working out since you rarely will create a class within the eval and then use meta-programming on it. For the other three this is different, but adding a flush cache we could have. Of course, if we use Closeable, we could use close instead. Adding this to GroovyShell and GroovyScriptEngine would be actually a good idea I think. GroovyClassLoader is because it is extending URLClassLoader, already closeable. So it could go there even without adding a new interface."

--- GitHub Pull-request comment (user: blackdrag)

Mentoring, why? _____

Not mentoring, why? _____

Not sure

Q9 PR Comment 8: "This seems like it might not be backward compatible with the existing Kafka-spout; i.e., the offsets in ZK are presumably not going to be stored exactly the same as they were before. Is there any plan for supporting migration from the current Kafka-spout to this one? "

--- GitHub Pull-request comment (user: erikdw)

Mentoring, why? _____

Not mentoring, why? _____

Not sure